

Preparation and Characterization of Talc and Calcium Carbonate Reinforced Polypropylene Hybrid Composite

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Abstract

Talc or Calcium Carbonate (CaCO₃) reinforced Polypropylene hybrid composites were prepared by melt blending method using hot press at 176°C. Thermal and mechanical properties of the hybrid composites were investigated by using Thermo gravimetric/Differential Thermal (TGA/DTA) analyzer and Universal Testing Machine (UTM) machine respectively and compared with those of pure PP and also with each other of single filler filled matrix. Increase in flexural and tensile modulus and better thermal stability were attained for hybrid composites at 5% of the filler (Talc or Calcium Carbonate) exfoliation. In addition, water absorption and biological degradation through soil burial test were also successfully done by increasing loading percentages of two fillers.

Keywords: Poly propylene; Composites; Fillers; Mechanical properties; Thermal properties; Biodegradation

Introduction

Poly propylene is on the hand and ordinary commodity polymer with a very simple chemical structure which is probably the most used mineral filled thermoplastic polymer [1]. Polymer based industries and their developments showed strong interest in manufacturing strong lightweight materials [2]. Mineral admixtures can be used as alternatives to replace different kinds of pure polymers depending on their availability and their field of applications [3]. Thermoplastic polymers and especially polyolefin are produced and consumed today in vast quantities. Lower static friction coefficient of thermoplastics show adhesion behavior to the thermoplastics working together with other materials and give better anti-wear properties. However, they are seldom used as pure polymers and are usually combined with mineral fillers [4].

Poly propylene is highly crystalline, favoring the generation of large spherulites and formation of cracks [5]. Therefore, neat poly propylene has poor flexural performance and low tensile modulus. Properties of poly propylene can be modified by introducing reinforcing filler and can understand their rheological behavior before and after modifying [6]. Depending on the type of reinforcement used, tensile strength and flexural strength can greatly affect. Thermal behavior of polypropylene as a semi-crystalline polymer noticeably changed by filler reinforcement [7].

Fillers find applications in the polymer industry almost exclusively, e.g., to improve mechanical, thermal, electrical properties and dimensional stability [5,8]. Polypropylene (PP) filled with particulate fillers are of great interest in both research and industry [5]. In recent years, researchers have focused on filler reinforced polymers as an alternative to traditional pure polymers [3,9,10]. Traditional fillers, such as non-ferrous metallic powders, kaolin, and some oxides improve tensile strength of polymer materials but a decrease in toughness and ductility.

The softest mineral talc uses in cosmetic industries and also in paint industries as an extender and filler pigment. It reduces the cost of composites and improves the performance of the polymer by increasing its tensile behavior and temperature performance [2]. CaCO₃ having isotropic particulate structure completely blends with high density polypropylene polymer and improves stiffness, hardness, chemical resistance and gas barrier properties [11].

This study is therefore aimed at reinforcing PP with commercial grade CaCO₃ and talc using relatively cheap technology (melt blending) with the view to determining the optimum filler load for the enhancement of both mechanical and thermal properties of the single filler hybrid composite. Thus, the work included with the preparation and characterization of PP-CaCO₃ and PP-talc composites and also the investigation of water uptake and biological degradation under certain time periods.

Experimental

Materials

The investigated polypropylene homopolymer with a melt flow index of 10 g/10 min (230°C, 2.16 kg) and a density of 0.8 g/cm³ was purchased from Japan. The fillers talc and calcium carbonate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany. The instrument used includes Paul-Otto Weber-Presser, Twin-screw Extruder, Universal Testing Machine, TGA Machine, Digital Balance and furnace.

Methods

At first 60 gm of Pure Poly propylene (PP) was weighted by an electric balance. Then this amount of PP was taken to drier and dried for about four hours to remove all moisture. Compounding was carried out passing the dried PP through a twin-screw extruder (model Rheomex CTW 150). The barrel temperature was kept at 170°C and the PP got melted. The calcium carbonate and talc were then added to the melt separately. Compounds were blended at 176°C by directly placing in hot press plate and pressed it by hydraulic presser. The plates were then cooled by water. After cooling to room temperature, the sheet was collected from plate cut into a specific shape to perform different tests [1]. The various composite formulations that were used in the study are shown in Table 1.

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Figure 1: Effects of the different filler loadings on the flexural strength of hybrid composites a) CaCO₃, b) Talc.

Figure 2: Effects of the different filler loadings on the tensile strength of CaCO₃ and Talc filled hybrid composites.

Figure 4: Thermo gravimetric-Differential Thermal Analysis (TG-DTA) curve for Pure Poly propylene.

Figure 3: Variation of water uptake as a function of filler content (Calcium carbonate and Talc).

Figure 5: Thermogravimetric-Differential Thermal Analysis (TG-DTA) curve for talc filled Poly propylene.

Characterization

Mechanical properties: Tensile testing is a fundamental materials science test in which a sample is subjected to uniaxial tension until failure. The tensile and flexural properties were measured with a universal testing machine 5565, USA in accordance with ASTM D-638. The cross-head speed of 10 mm/min and a load cell of 500 N were used. For flexural tests, a three-point loading system was used and support span length was adjusted to 50 mm. The measurements were done at room temperature [12].

Flexural strength (or the modulus of rupture) is the amount of force an object can take without breaking or permanently deforming. For a rectangular sample under a load in a three-point bending setup.

$$\text{Flexure strength} = \frac{3 \times \text{Load at fracture point} \times \text{Length of the support span}}{2 \times \text{Width} \times \text{Thickness}^2}$$

Tensile strength is calculated by dividing the load at break by the original minimum cross-sectional area.

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \frac{\text{Load at break}}{\text{Original width} \times \text{Original thickness}}$$

Water absorption: Mechanical properties of polymer are affected negatively with water absorption. Polymers which absorb water tend to change dimension in the process and when water stability is required in products made of such polymer composites, grades with less tendency to absorb water are chosen.

In order to measure the water absorption characteristics of the composites, rectangular specimens were prepared. The specimens

The water absorption tendency of PP-CaCO₃ and PP-talc composite is shown in Figure 3. Composite with 15 wt% CaCO₃ displayed highest water absorption capacity (0.015%) at 360 hours. Composite with 5% talc addition showed the lowest water absorption capacity of 0.008 wt% after 360 hours. Thus, 5% PP-talc composite was seen to have superior water absorption resistance over all other composite formulations [4]. Since mechanical and electrical properties of polymer composites are affected negatively with water absorption, the prepared composites have significant stability against moisture and environment.

Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) is a powerful tool for assessing thermal stability and thermal decomposition behavior of polymers and their composites. Thermo-gravimetric Analysis (TGA) measures the amount and rate of change in the weight of a material as a function of temperature or time in a controlled atmosphere [14]. Figures 4-6 shows the weight loss temperature curves (TG) and the first derivative of TG curves (DTG) of pure PP and hybrid composites containing either CaCO₃ or talc as filler.

Peak degradation temperature (DTG peak) corresponded to the weight loss rate where the maximum degradation occurs. Furthermore, the mass loss percentage is obtained from the TGA curve at the DTG peak. From the above figures, it can be observed that the hybrid composites were the material thermally more stable with an increase of about 10°C compared to the pure PP. By comparing two curves in Figures 5 and 6, it was clear that the thermal stability of CaCO₃-PP composite was higher than the Talc-PP composite due to radicals released by thermal degradation more easily in calcium carbonate than talc which could participate in partial crosslinking of PP chains resulting greater thermally stable composite. The residue present at last for both composite was near to 15%, which indicated the fillers were properly distributed through the PP matrix [1]. The melting temperature of the CaCO₃-PP composite was higher than that of Talc-PP composite and also the degradation rate of CaCO₃-PP composite was higher than Talc-PP composite.

Biological degradation

Degradation is assessed by measuring the decay of relevant physical properties such as: changes in molecular weight mass and molecular mass distribution, tensile properties, mass loss, morphological changes, etc.

Significant biological degradation was not occurred in cases of both pure and hybrid composites measured in terms of weight loss over the test period time as shown in Figure 7. Because the suitable condition for growth of enzyme was not present here because of their hydrophobicity. But it must be appreciated that enzymes commonly produced by fungi were not capable of penetrating the composite sheet and so the blocking of enzyme activity was a significant mechanism [13].

Conclusion

This study gave a true picture of how the different fillers interact with the PP matrix. Both talc and CaCO₃ fillers had significant effects on the PP matrix. It is worthy to note that useful composites could be successfully developed using CaCO₃ as reinforcing filler into polymer

matrix that of PP. Mechanical properties, measured in terms of tensile and flexural strength demonstrated that filler used in this work acted as effective reinforcing agents for thermoplastic polymers. The flexural and tensile strength of the composites showed an increasing trend for 5% and then decreased with further increases in filler content due to poor adhesion of fillers. Water uptake for these composites was not significantly changed with increase in filler loading. Because filler does not contain any hydrophilic group. Finally to summarize, the better reinforcing effect of CaCO₃ filler as compared to talc filler in PP matrix had indicated its suitability as reinforcing filler for thermoplastic polymer. Our study may help to design and development of high performance PP hybrid composites.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Aguilar H, Pedram M, Toro P, Quijada R, Ángel M, et al. (2014) Synergic effect of two inorganic fillers on the mechanical and thermal properties of hybrid polypropylene composites. *J Chil Chem Soc* 2: 2468-2473.
2. Balakrishna NS, Ismail H, Othman N (2013) Processing, Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Polypropylene/Rattan Powder/Talc Hybrid Composites. *BioResources* 8: 6409-6423.
3. Aljerf L (2015) Effect of Thermal-cured Hydraulic Cement Admixtures on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete. *International Ceramic Review* 64: 346-356.
4. Adeosun SO, Usman MA, Ayoola WA, Bodude MA (2013) Physico mechanical responses of polypropylene-CaCO₃ composite. *Minerals and Materials Characterization and Engineering* 1: 145-152.
5. Leong YW, Ishak ZAM, Ariffin A (2003) Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Talc and Calcium Carbonate Filled Polypropylene Hybrid Composites. *Journal of Applied Polymer* 91: 3327-3336.
6. Resources M, Campus E, Selatan SP (2009) Relationship of Rheological Study with Morphological Characteristics of Multicomponent (Talc and Calcium Carbonate) Filled Polypropylene Hybrid Composite. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 28: 2577-2587.
7. Composites GP (2019) Shrinkage Optimization in Talc- and Glass-Fiber-Reinforced Polypropylene Composites. *Materials* 12: 1-20.
8. Leong YW, Bakar MBA, Ishak ZAM, Ariffin A (2004) Characterization of talc/calcium carbonate filled polypropylene hybrid composites weathered in a natural environment. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 83: 411-422.
9. Oladele IO, Daramola OO (2014) Effect of Chemical Treatment on the Mechanical Properties of Sisal Fibre Reinforced Polyester Composites. *Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies*, pp: 1-12.
10. Haddar N, Mnif N (2017) Effect on Morphology and Mechanical Properties Abstract. *Polymer Science* 3: 1-7.
11. Weon J, Sue H (2006) Mechanical properties of talc- and CaCO₃-reinforced high-crystallinity polypropylene composites. *Journal of Materials Science* 41: 2291-2300.
12. Ariffin A, Jikan SS, Samsudin MSF, Ariff ZM, Ishak ZAM (2006) Melt Elasticity Phenomenon of Multicomponent (Talc and Calcium Carbonate) Filled Polypropylene. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 25: 913-923.
13. Pelacho AM (2016) Degradation of agricultural biodegradable plastics in the soil under laboratory conditions. *Journal of Environmental Management*, pp: 216-224.
14. Yetkin SH, Karadeniz B, Güleşen M (2017) Investigation of thermal properties of graphene oxide/polyimide resin composites. *Polypropylene Composites* 38: 2321-2331.